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AS AN INTERVENTION IN IMPROVING THE PRONUNCIATION
COMPETENCE AMONG GRADE 7 STUDENTS**

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Utilization of Project DICE (Dice It, Create, and Enunciate) as an Intervention in Improving the Pronunciation Competence among Grade 7 Students

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Abstract

This quantitative descriptive study aimed to investigate how Project DICE (DICE IT, CREATE, AND ENUNCIATE) affects pronunciation competence among Grade 7 Rose students at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. It measured Strategies in Talking, Stress on Compound Words, and Strategies for Stress Intonation. Forty-four students participated by completing a survey questionnaire before and after the intervention. Before the intervention, scores were 1.89 for Strategies in Talking, 1.92 for Stress on Compound Words, and 1.90 for Strategies for Stress Intonation, with an average mean of 1.90, indicating low pronunciation competence. After the intervention, scores increased to 4.39 for Strategies in Talking, 4.40 for Stress on Compound Words, and 4.60 for Strategies for Stress Intonation, with an overall average of 4.46, indicating significant improvement. This demonstrated that Project DICE (DICE IT, CREATE, AND ENUNCIATE) effectively enhanced students' pronunciation competence. Additionally, the study investigated the effectiveness of Project DICE (DICE IT, CREATE, AND ENUNCIATE) and gathered insights from teachers and students. Fourteen participants, including students and teachers from the same school, took part in in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The data revealed three themes regarding the effectiveness of Project DICE (DICE IT, CREATE, AND ENUNCIATE) in developing pronunciation competence: Enhancement of Communication Skills, Increased Student Confidence, and Improved Reading Skills. Furthermore, four themes emerged from the insights shared by teachers and students: Improving Students' Pronunciation Skills, Enhancing Reading Competence, serving as a Teacher's Tool for Effective English Teaching, and Encouraging Dedication and Self-Motivation. These findings confirmed that Project DICE (DICE IT, CREATE, AND ENUNCIATE) significantly improved the pronunciation competence of Grade 7 Rose students.

Keywords: *pronunciation competence, Grade 7 students, quantitative study*

Introduction

One linguistic skill that is taught in primary school is reading, which is meant to help the students comprehend the significance of the text in order for them to understand the text's contents accurately and thoroughly. Therefore, students can find learning easier because of their reading skills. With reading and also writing skills, an individual can comprehend various kinds of information (Saonah, 2018).

Globally, difficulty in pronunciation is one of the most difficult parts of reading especially in non-native English language speakers. Asia is still facing struggle in pronouncing words especially those in far-flung areas and those which do not have accessibility in technology such as reading materials. Particularly, Myanmar and Cambodia are struggling due to lack of resources, EFL (English as a foreign language) teachers, and English language is not people's mother tongue. Usually these places have high percentage of people who struggle literacy skills such as pronouncing words and it affects how they learn English language (Khalif, 2019).

In the Philippines, a survey conducted by The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) Results from PISA 2018, 80% of the Filipino students did not reach the average level of reading proficiency. The Filipino students scored lower than those countries and economies that participated in PISA 2018 among the survey of proficiency in reading, especially in pronunciation (Claessen et al., 2020).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School most of the students in Grade 7 are struggling to pronounce English words. Some of them are having difficulties to pronounce phrases and words that seem unfamiliar to them. The school did not have any programs related to enhancing the pronunciation proficiency of the struggling students. There is an existing problem in terms of the reading difficulties of the students which is mostly present in the Grade 7 level. Thus, the reading problem of the students hinder them to understand and comprehend sentences and instructions.

The study has social relevance because this is anticipated to produce solution to problem. Particularly, creating intervention in difficulty of reading pronunciation among Grade 7 students in a particular school in the Province of Davao del Norte. Moreover, teachers will be able to use this one as a reference to help aid the problems arising when reading English words to help learner become effective readers. The study warranted immediate research attention because pronunciation have brought to the learners of the particular institution. As such, this study must be conducted right now to help teachers to find a way to lessen reading problems like pronunciation and to help the students to aid the problem that causes their literacy performance become weak due to pronunciation difficulty.

Despite the mentioned studies, there were no studies that focused on the pronunciation difficulty in the locality of Kapalong. Other studies only focused on creating intervention about the spelling and reading comprehension. The study of Lundberg (2020) entitled

“Applying Peer Tutoring to Spelling with Elementary-Aged Students” creating an intervention about difficulty in spelling the words among elementary students. On the other hand, the study of Duff (2019) entitled “The Effect of Vocabulary Intervention on Text Comprehension” is focused on creating an intervention about vocabulary as reading comprehension was the main problem of this research. The two mentioned studies are far different from our study because our problem was about word pronunciation that need to be given intervention among Grade 7 students in the Province of Davao del Norte. This is anticipated to help students struggling in pronouncing words to help them improve in literacy and to learn better. This, therefore, establishes the research gap of the study.

Proposed Intervention

The project DICE (Dice it, Create, and Enunciate) serves as a project and intervention that aims to provide pronunciation enhancement through integrating the said intervention as an activity in the teaching-learning process. It can be through collaborative learning and social cognitive learning. The program provides fun activity learning designed especially for grade seven students who struggle with pronouncing words. The main goal of the intervention is to provide engaging and effective activity focusing on learners’ pronunciation difficulties. The purpose of this activity was to provide with effective yet entertaining activity so that students’ challenges with pronunciation can be addressed more interestingly.

Furthermore, during the implementation of the intervention, the materials would be mainly dice with words on each side. The teacher would start from an easy level. When teachers make sure that the students achieve the first level, that was the time for the teacher to proceed to the other levels. Moreover, the teacher may use the learning materials to foster collaborative learning through peer tutoring. When the learning process interactive, the more the students would be intrinsically motivated to learn, and the teacher would act as a guide on the side.

In addition to the teaching process, the instructor would organize collaborative games for the students using dice. One such game, "Right, Left, Center," requires students to roll the dice and pair the word rolled with words to the left or right. Subsequently, students were tasked with vocalizing these word pairings. Another activity, "Two Dice at a Time for a Word," involves group work where two dice were rolled, and the resulting words are paired and vocalized. An additional game entitled "Complete as I Dice" involves selecting a group to roll the dice, with the second group following suit. The syllables derived from the words are then combined and vocalized. The game "Dice like a Wise" involves a representative from each group rolling a dice, with the number determining the number of words to be read from the words displayed on the screen. Finally, "Fill and Full," a game in which the teacher rolls the dice to correspond with specific words, emphasizes the importance of precision in pronunciation. Throughout these activities, students would be grouped into teams of two or three to engage in word pronunciation exercises such as identifying rhyming pairs and minimal pairs.

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative descriptive research design was used as an approach. This research design was used as it would allow the researcher to achieve the study’s objectives. As explained, in this type of research design, it gathers numerical data wherein it focused on determining the means. As well as, it is descriptive as there were interviews made to come up with the themes used to completely analyze the data (Bhandari, 2020).

Participants

The study participants were Grade 7 Rose students at Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School at Capungagan, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Forty-four participants (44) participated with the said intervention before, during, and after. Additionally, there were fourteen (14) participants in the in-depth interview and focus-group discussion in which, seven (7) for in-depth interviews and seven (7) for focus-group discussion consist of both teachers and students.

In addition, the section Grade-7 Rose was selected as the participants of the said intervention because most of the students could not pronounce words properly. It was determined during the English class of one of the researchers of this study. Some issues were mispronounced of words by interchanging of consonant sounds (f) and (p). Others do not really know how to pronounce basic words. Therefore, there was a need for the conduct of action research.

Procedure

The researchers followed the subsequent procedures when collecting the data to obtain the required information for the investigation. First is Crafting of Questionnaire - Pretest and Post-test Questionnaires: The researcher-initiated group planning sessions to develop questionnaires for both pretest and post-test assessments. Next is Questionnaire Validation. The researchers sought validation of the questionnaire from experts or a panel well-versed in questionnaire development to ensure its validity and reliability. Then, the Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study comes next. The researchers asked the school principal to distribute the pre-test questionnaires to the identified students having difficulty in pronunciation. The Pretest Assessment Administration, Intervention Implementation, and Post-test Assessment Administration follow. Lastly, data tabulation and evaluation are next. The gathered data from the pretest and post-test underwent tabulation.

Data Analysis

The computation of data and the hypotheses were tested at the significance level of alpha 0.05, involves the utilization of various statistical tools. These tools employed to ensure accurate analysis and interpretation of the data.

Mean. This refers to the average and is calculated by dividing the sum of the students' scores in the assessment. It is used to determine the level of pronunciation competency of the students before and after the intervention.

T-test. In this research, the t-test will be used to determine whether the two-population means are different. It also helps to determine significant differences in terms of pronunciation competence in pretest and post-test.

The researchers used thematic analysis to identify the emerging themes that emerged from the study which was coming from the responses of the participants. It was done by clustering responses which shared the same thought and idea then was categorized based on the shared emerging theme with an assigned code and assigned theme. To check the credibility of the theme, the assigned themes from the thematic analysis was checked and further validated by experts.

Results and Discussion

Research Objective No. 1.1: To determine the level of pronunciation competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE.

To find the answer for the first research objective, the researchers used and adopted a questionnaire to suit the context of the study. The set of the questionnaires dealt with the student pronunciation with the indicators on Strategies in Talking, Stress on Compound Words, and Strategies for Stress and Intonation. As shown in Table 1 were the mean for the indicator in student's pronunciation competence before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Strategies in Talking.

Table 1. *Level Of Pronunciation Competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE in Terms of Strategies in Talking*

<i>Strategies in Talking</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I look up different sounds in dictionary and hear them pronounced.	1.59	Very Low	3.93	High
2. I practice consonants and vowels in words before I say them in a sentence.	1.77	Very Low	4.39	Very High
3. I practice sounds after I figure out how to pronounce them	1.89	Low	4.07	High
4. I practice using repetition.	2.00	Low	4.39	Very High
5. In order to improve my sounds, I listen to online/recorded materials.	1.75	Very Low	4.68	Very High
6. I practice saying new words while speaking.	2.07	Low	4.41	Very High
7. I imitate words that I hear unfamiliar.	1.95	Low	4.59	Very High
8. I group words with the same sounds and pronounce it.	2.14	Low	4.48	Very High
9. I ask my teacher if I have correct pronunciation.	2.02	Low	4.64	Very High
10. I record myself and repeatedly hear each word I said to make sure that my pronunciation is correct.	1.73	Very Low	4.41	Very High
Overall	1.89	Low	4.40	Very High

The table 1 showed the strategies in talking overall score in pre-test of 1.89, which descriptively meant low. While after the intervention, it had an overall score of 4.40, descriptively meant very high. The result interpreted that the student's level of pronunciation competence in terms of strategies in talking had developed and students had increased engagement across strategies. As supported by Guo (2020), students learn the strategies once they are guided, especially in terms of pronouncing unfamiliar words. Students best pronounce words on strategies made through practice and repetition,

Additionally, the highest mean in pre-test is 2.14 which descriptively meant low. The mean is from the item 8 - I group words with the same sounds and pronounce it, which meant that this is less observed. It implied that students did not know this strategy that was why, they encountered pronunciation difficulty. On the other hand, the highest mean in post test is 4.68 which descriptively meant very high. This is from the item 5 - In order to improve my sounds, I listen to online/recorded materials. which meant that this strategy is always observed after the intervention. The result implied that the intervention helped students to strategized such as listening online to improve pronunciation. This is the same with the study of Rost (2022) that audio materials play a crucial role in language learning by providing learners with exposure to authentic spoken language. Listening to audio recordings allows learners to encounter natural pronunciation, intonation, and language use, which are essential for developing listening comprehension skills.

Furthermore, the lowest mean in pre-test is 1.59, descriptively meant very low. The mean is from the item 1- I look up different sounds in dictionary and hear them pronounced, which meant this strategy is never observed. The result implied that students never used this strategy resulting to pronunciation difficulty. Contrastingly, the lowest mean in posttest is 3.93, which descriptively meant high. This mean is from the item 1- I look up different sounds in dictionary and hear them pronounced, which means that the strategy is often observed. The result showed that there is an improvement of this strategy after the intervention and students often search in dictionary

for a sound to help improve their pronunciation.

Moreover, the other remaining indicators in pre-test had a mean range from 1.77 which descriptively meant very low up to 2.07, descriptively meant low. The result revealed that the students' level of pronunciation competence in terms of Strategies in Talking was never and rarely observed that was why, students struggle in pronunciation. Nonetheless, the remaining indicators in posttest range from 4.07 which descriptively meant high up to 4.64 which descriptively meant very high. The result unveiled that the intervention helped the students to use strategies in talking to help their pronunciation competence increase as it is often and always observed.

Research Objective No. 1.2: To determine the level of pronunciation competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Stress on Compound Words.

To find the answer for the first research objective, the researchers used and adopted a questionnaire to suit the context of the study. The set of the questionnaires dealt with the student pronunciation with the indicators on Strategies in Talking, Stress on Compound Words, and Strategies for Stress and Intonation. As shown in Table 1 were the mean for the indicator in student's pronunciation competence before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Stress on Compound Words.

Table 2. *Level of Pronunciation Competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Stress on Compound Words in Terms of Stress on Compound Words*

<i>Stress on Compound Words</i>	<i>Pretest</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
11. I look up long words in dictionary to find out which syllable receives the main stress.	2.80	Moderate	4.45	Very High
12. I consult pronunciation materials (textbook, online resources, software programs) to decide how to stress words.	2.59	Low	4.45	Very High
13. I repeatedly read long words to assess and/or correct my pronunciation.	2.32	Low	4.52	Very High
14. I read aloud long words in order to improve them.	1.68	Very Low	4.30	Very High
15. I use difficult words in conversation so that I can improve how I pronounce them.	1.77	Very Low	4.39	Very High
16. I listen recorded words (Electronic dictionary, pronunciation materials)	1.34	Very Low	4.23	Very High
17. I listen to academic lectures to improve my ability to pronounce long words.	1.41	Very Low	4.32	Very High
18. I use spelling rules to decide which syllable to stress in a word.	1.64	Very Low	4.43	Very High
19. I draw stresses on top of words to remind me which syllables receive main stresses.	1.95	Low	4.59	Very High
20. I use words I practice more often to remember the patterns of pronunciation.	2.11	Low	4.36	Very High
Overall	1.96	Low	4.40	Very High

The table 1.2 showed the stress on compound words overall score in pre-test of 1.96 which descriptively meant low. Whereas, after the intervention, it had an overall score of 4.40, descriptively meant very high. The result interpreted that the students' level of pronunciation competence in terms of stress in compound words developed and always observed.

In addition, the highest mean in pre-test is 2.80 which descriptively meant moderate. The mean is from the item 1 - I look up long words in dictionary to find out which syllable receives the main stress, which meant that this is less observed. It implied that the students sometimes listen to recorded words that was why they still encountered pronunciation difficulty. On the other hand, the highest mean in posttest is 4.59 which descriptively meant very high. This is from the item 19 - I draw stresses on top of words to remind me which syllables receive main stresses, which meant that this strategy is always observed after the intervention. The result implied that the intervention helped students put stress on compound words such as putting marks on words to be reminded of how it was being pronounced to help students develop pronunciation competence. According to James (2021), the study asserts that dictionaries play a crucial role in supporting second language learners in achieving accurate pronunciation through access to phonetic information and audio resources as dictionaries are teachers' materials to facilitate the teaching of English language, thereby facilitating more effective language learning outcomes.

Further, the lowest mean in pre-test is 1.41, descriptively meant very low. The mean is from the item 17- I listen to academic lectures to improve my ability to pronounce long words, which meant this is never observed. The result implied that students never listen to lectures especially highlighting pronunciation resulting to pronunciation difficulty in long words. Contrastingly, the lowest mean in posttest is 4.23, which descriptively meant very high. This mean is from the item 16 - I listen recorded words (Electronic dictionary, pronunciation materials), which meant that it is often observed. The result showed that there is an improvement on the stress on compound words after the intervention and students often listen audio materials to help improve their pronunciation. According to Thomas (2021) dice games provide a structured yet enjoyable method for students to develop their understanding and application of stress patterns in compound words, contributing to enhanced pronunciation competence in language learning contexts.

On the same hand, the other remaining indicators in pre-test had a mean range from 1.41 which descriptively meant very low up to 2.59, descriptively meant low. The result revealed that the students' level of pronunciation competence in terms of Stress on Compound

Words was never and rarely observed that was why, students struggle in pronunciation. Nonetheless, the remaining indicators in posttest range from 4.32 which descriptively meant very high up to 4.52 which descriptively meant very high. The result unveiled that the intervention helped the students to stress on compound words to help their pronunciation competence increase as it is always observed.

Research Objective No.1. 3: To determine the level of pronunciation competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Strategies for Stress and Intonation

To find the answer for the first research objective, the researchers used and adopted a questionnaire to suit the context of the study. The set of the questionnaires dealt with the student pronunciation with the indicators on Strategies in Talking, Stress on Compound Words, and Strategies for Stress and Intonation. As shown in Table 1 were the mean for the indicator in student's pronunciation competence before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Strategies for Stress and Intonation.

Table 3. Level of Pronunciation Competence among Grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of Project DICE in terms of Strategies for Stress and Intonation

<i>Strategies for Stress and Intonation</i>	<i>Pretest</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
21. I follow my instinct to figure out the stress and intonation of each phrase.	1.91	Low	4.61	Very High
22. I decide the primary stressed and intonation of a word based on its meaning.	1.93	Low	4.75	Very High
23. I repeat the primary stress and intonation of a phrase or sentence based what I hear on the TV/Radio/Internet.	1.66	Very Low	4.77	Very High
24. I repeat pronouncing the after phrase or sentence from the teacher or recording.	1.73	Very Low	4.50	Very High
25. I practice primary stress on my own by reading aloud sentences and dialogs.	1.95	Low	4.66	Very High
26. I record myself saying the phrase or sentences to assess my pronunciation.	2.00	Low	4.43	Very High
27. I self-correct my pronunciation while speaking a phrase or dialogs.	1.82	Very Low	4.57	Very High
28. I divide my sentences into meaningful phrases before I read them aloud.	1.93	Low	4.61	Very High
29. I listen to news English broadcasts.	1.70	Very Low	4.66	Very High
30. I request native speakers'/teachers' feedback on my pronunciation.	1.95	Low	4.48	Very High
Overall	1.86	Low	4.60	Very High

The table 1.3 showed strategies for stress and intonation overall score in pre-test of 1.86 which descriptively meant low. Whereas, after the intervention, it had an overall score of 4.60, descriptively meant very high. The result interpreted that the students' level of pronunciation competence in terms of strategies for stress and Intonation developed and always observed.

In addition, the highest mean in pre-test is 2.00 which descriptively meant low. The mean is from the item 26 - I record myself saying the phrase or sentences to assess my pronunciation, which meant that this is less observed. It implied that the students rarely record themselves to assess their pronunciation that was why they still encountered pronunciation difficulty. On the other hand, the highest mean in posttest is 4.77 which descriptively meant very high. This is from the item 23 - I repeat the primary stress and intonation of a phrase or sentence based what I hear on the TV/Radio/Internet, which means that imitating the heard word from various sources is always observed after the intervention. The result implied that the intervention helped students strategize for stress and intonation such as imitating the heard words to be reminded of how it was being pronounced to help students develop pronunciation competence.

Further, the lowest mean in pre-test is 1.66, descriptively meant very low. The mean is from the item 23- I repeat the primary stress and intonation of a phrase or sentence based what I hear on the TV/Radio/Internet, which meant this is never observed. The result implied that students never imitate how phrase or sentences are pronounced resulting to difficulty in pronunciation. Contrastingly, the lowest mean in posttest is 4.43, which descriptively meant very high. This mean is from the item 26 - I record myself saying the phrase or sentences to assess my pronunciation, which means that it is always observed. The result showed that there was an improvement on the strategies for stress and intonation after the intervention and students always record and self-assess to help improve their pronunciation. Dalla (2019) supported that self-assessment played a crucial role to enhance students' pronunciation. Thus, students need to realize that the proper stress of syllable and intonation are the keys to effective language learning.

On the same hand, the other remaining indicators in pre-test had a mean range from 1.70 which descriptively meant very low up to 1.95, descriptively meant low. The result revealed that the students' level of pronunciation competence in terms of strategies for stress and intonation was never and rarely observed that was why, students struggle in pronunciation. Nonetheless, the remaining indicators in posttest range from 4.48 which descriptively meant very high up to 4.75 which descriptively meant very high. The result unveiled that the intervention helped the students to strategize for stress and intonation help their pronunciation competence increase as it is always observed. As asserted by Jao (2021), words matter on stress and intonation, especially when used in context. Proper strategy is one of the key factors to effectively enhance pronunciation among EFL learners.

Summary on the level of pronunciation competence among grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of project DICE

Table 4 provides a summary of the students' pronunciation competence with regard to strategies in talking, stress on compound words, and strategies for stress and intonation. Below is the analysis and summary of each indicator.

Table 4. *Summary on the level of pronunciation competence among grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of project DICE*

<i>Problem Solving Skills</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
Strategies in Talking	1.89	Low	4.40	Very High
Stress on Compound Words	1.96	Low	4.40	Very High
Strategies for Stress and Intonation	1.86	Low	4.60	Very High
Overall	1.90	Low	4.47	Very High

Shown in Table 4 are the average scores for the pronunciation competence indicators, which have a 1.90 overall mean score in pre-test which descriptively meant low. The low level may be explained by the respondents' low ratings for most of the metrics. This indicates that the items related to that the strategies in talking, stress on compound words, and strategies for stress and intonations were rarely manifested by the students.

The highest mean in pre-test is 1.96, which descriptively meant low. It is from the indicator stress on compound words. This meant that students stress on compound words were majorly never observed. On the other hand, the highest mean in posttest is 4.60 which descriptively meant very high. It is from the indicator strategies for stress and intonation. It means that it was always observed from the students after the intervention. The result implied that students strategize to pronounce words properly based on its stress and intonation. This result was supported by Hode (2022) stated that interactive games help students develop strategies on how to pronounce words properly such as learning the syllables and its stress and proper intonation of phrases and sentences. Games in the classroom is one way to introduce learners about the accurate pronunciation that led them to create strategies on their own to become effective reader and speaker of English language.

The lowest mean in pre-test is 1.86 which descriptively meant low. This is from the indicator strategies for stress and intonation. The result unveiled that before the intervention. Students rarely strategize on how to pronounce phrases and sentence properly based on its stress and intonation. On the contrary, the lowest mean in posttest is 4.40 which descriptively meant very high. It is from the indicators strategies in talking and stress on compound words. The study implies that students always strategize on how they talk and focus on learning the long words to increase their pronunciation competence. As highlighted by Gadd (2022), long words are the hardest to pronounce, that is why, games imposed in the classroom would help students to discover strategies to learn how to pronounce compound words effectively.

Research Objective No. 2: Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Posttest

To find the answer for the first research objective, the researchers used and adopted a questionnaire to suit the context of the study. The set of the questionnaires dealt with the student pronunciation with the indicators on Strategies in Talking, Stress on Compound Words, and Strategies for Stress and Intonation. As shown in Table 5 were the result and interpretation of the data indicating if there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test.

Table 5. *Significant Difference Between Pre-test and Posttest*

<i>Type of Test</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision = . 0</i>
Pretest	44	43	1.09	0.158	-98.369	< .001	Significant
Post-Test	44		4.47	0.106			

Table 5 shows the significant difference between the pre-test which has a mean score of 1.09 and posttest with a mean score of 4.47 respectively. The data demonstrates a significant improvement in students' performance from the pre-test to the post-test. The mean score increased from 1.09 to 4.47, and the high t-value and very low P-value indicate that this improvement is statistically significant. This suggests that the intervention was highly effective in enhancing the students' skills or knowledge in the assessed area. The consistency in the post-test scores, indicated by the lower standard deviation, also reflects a uniform benefit across the sample group. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test.

Accordingly, dice game was one of the most effective ways for learners to learn. Interactive games that use gestures or body motions to promote sound production. This hands-on technique keeps children interested and improves muscle memory for proper pronunciation (Saidi 2020). Interactive games such as dice games are attractive games for learners through incorporating effective classroom management and teaching pedagogy, language teaching is effective, especially in non-native speakers as it enhances the essential macro skills of students (Cadon, 2022).

Research Question No. 1: Effectiveness of Project DICE on Developing Pronunciation Competence of Students

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews and focus group discussion were conducted with the informants and participants. Probing questions were asked to elicit their concept regarding their observation and experiences with the effectiveness of the Project DICE on developing the pronunciation competence of the students. The major themes and supporting statements for research question number 1 were presented in Table 3. Participants had their responses to their own experiences and observation. From the answers of the participants, three major themes emerged: (1) enhancement of communication skills; (2) increase students' confidence; and (3)

improving students reading skills.

Table 6. *Themes and Supporting Statements on the Effectiveness of Project DICE on Developing Pronunciation Competence of Students*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Enhancement of Communication Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I can easily relay the message or things that I wanted to say and share to my classmates or friends in the classroom.” (FGD - 01) • “During our class discussions, I have noticed that most of my students can easily understand the words that I have said and also they can now be able to communicate during our discussions.” (IDI-03) • “Whenever I am in my class, the students can catch up the lesson even though some words are difficult for them to understand, but because of this project, I have observed that they can now communicate and understand words I am referring.” (IDI-04) • “I am now able to exchange words to my classmates and also, I can now communicate using English words during our class discussion. Particularly in giving my responses and sharing my ideas in class.”(FGD-03) • “Whenever I have a conversation with my classmates, I am confident to talk to them using English words and I am now confident to pronounce such words.” (IDI-02)
Increase Students’ Confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I observed that my students are participating actively during our class discussion especially in our English class. They volunteer to read some phrases during our class and I have observed that they can now really read English words.” (IDI-01) • “Upon the implementation of this project, I have noticed that the pronunciation of the students did really improve, especially in pronouncing English phrases. They are now capable to express their ideas in class discussions confidently using the English language, particularly in oral recitations and also in essay writing assessments.” (IDI-05) • “During our classes, especially in English class, I am really not confident in giving or sharing my ideas or even when I am called by my teacher to answer some questions because there are words that I am not familiar and I cannot really read and understand. But, after having this project by our student-teachers, I learned some techniques in pronouncing English words. And now, I am confident and be able to express my ideas in class.” (FGD-05)
Improving Students’ Reading Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The students can now able to read the unfamiliar English words and also, they can pronounce it properly. Even though I used an English word that have same spelling but different pronunciation, they can now pronounce and read it effectively.”(IDI-03) • “Before, I have a hard time to read the English words especially the words that I am not familiar about, but after the project that been conducted by my student-teachers, there are strategies and techniques that I have learned which it helps me on how to read English words.” (FGD-03) • “After and during the implementation of this project by the student- teachers, I have observed that the reading skills of the students have improved. They can now read English phrases and when we have reading class or activity, they can now really read and I am happy as their teacher about these improvements.” (IDI-04) • “Since primary years, I am really not into reading English phrases and words, that is why until now I am struggling to read and pronounce English words, but after the activity done by our student- teachers here in our classroom, I am now be able to love reading and I can now pronounce difficult and unfamiliar words that I thought before as difficult to pronounce and read.” (FGD-04)

In the study, it was found that Grade 7 students encountered and observed the effectiveness of Project DICE. They shared that it has the result in terms of enhancement of their communication skills. This was supported by the study conducted, which stated that research has indicated that training and teaching in pronunciation were positively correlated with enhanced communication abilities. The study revealed that learners’ level of communication as well as their pronunciation increased with focused pronunciation instruction. Furthermore, students who had pronunciation instruction speak more clearly and fluently in speaking (Derwing & Munro, 2018).

Moreover, the study revealed that students experienced an increase in their speaking confidence, which was also noted by their teachers after Project DICE was implemented. Effective pronunciation is a crucial aspect of reading and speaking skills. Consequently, by improving their pronunciation, students can enhance their confidence and their ability to socialize and participate. This is further supported by Escandallo and Baradillo (2024), who emphasize the pivotal role of students' speaking skills in social literacy and in boosting their engagement.

In addition, the students also experienced an improvement in their reading skills, which was also observed by the teachers during their class discussions and in every session of their catch-up Friday which was all about reading. This was heightened by Torgesen (2018) by emphasized that fluency in reading is directly correlated with teaching and training in pronunciation. Students read more fluently

and with greater comprehension when they can pronounce words correctly.

Conclusions

As researchers and future English language educators, it is vital to give importance to the emerging problems that the Philippine education system has faced today, especially pronunciation incompetence as this is a part of the reading and speaking skills. It helps people to understand written texts and to communicate effectively across the globe. Doing this research was quite hard because it takes courage, determination, hard work, persistence, and sacrifice to make this research successful. However, the love for teaching and the demand for accurate strategies in teaching the English language were very high to the point that we aim to be the catalyst for change. Being an English as a Foreign Language nation is not a hindrance to competing globally. This basic skill could positively impact not just inside the four corners of classrooms, but in real life and for the students' bright future. Moreover, students' confidence in speaking in reading could be improved with the help of our intervention, by making it fun, engaging, and comprehensive. Ensuring that as they proceed to higher levels, teachers will not suffer from this problem anymore.

The process of this action research was not easy. We faced self-doubts, self-discouragement, and lack of financial support. However, it did not hinder us to do our job. More than being a researcher, we knew in our hearts that this intervention would be a powerful tool to enlighten the minds of students that reading and speaking were not hard with proper pronunciation. We have realized that hardships occur only at the start, but when you proceed, you will realize that it was not as hard as you thought. It gives relief in our hearts knowing that our intervention was not wasted and it caused a positive impact on the students, teachers, institution, and to the Department of Education. With this, we encourage the other researchers to focus on problems especially targeting the macro skills. This action research would serve as a blueprint as to what other problems could be resolved using Project DICE, or what other intervention could be made with the same problem we had solved about pronunciation.

This study has successfully attained its objectives which are to determine the level of pronunciation competence among grade 7 Rose students before and after the implementation of project DICE, the significant difference between pre-test and posttest, and the effectiveness and insights shared by the students and teachers to the academe. Since this research is limited in many aspects. It is highly recommended for researchers that future studies should expand the sample size to enhance generalizability and conduct longitudinal research to assess the long-term effectiveness of Project DICE. Comparative analyses with other pronunciation interventions and incorporating technology, such as language learning apps, should also be explored.

In addition, for students, active participation in Project DICE activities and regular practice of the taught strategies are crucial. Seeking feedback from teachers and peers will help refine their pronunciation skills. For teachers, engaging in professional development programs focused on Project DICE and other effective pronunciation strategies is recommended. Incorporating varied pronunciation strategies, creating a supportive learning environment, and regularly monitoring student progress with constructive feedback are essential practices. Lastly, these recommendations build on the current study's findings, ensuring effective implementation and further research to enhance students' pronunciation competence and overall language acquisition.

References

- Bhandari, P. (2020) An Introduction to Quantitative Research. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research>
- Cadon, S. (2022). Use of songs, rhymes and games in teaching English to young learners in Bangladesh. *Dhaka University Journal of Linguistics*, 2(3), 161-172.
- Celce-Murcia, M., & Goodwin, J.M. (2018). *Teaching Pronunciation: A Reference for Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages*. Cambridge University Press.
- Claessen, M., Dzidic, P., Boyes, M., Badcock, N., Nayton, M., & Leitao, S. (2020). Educator's perceptions of the impact of reading difficulties for young people. *Australian Journal of Learning Difficulties*, 25, 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19404158.2020.1734952>
- Derwing, T.M., & Munro, M.J. (2018). Second language accent and pronunciation teaching: A Research-Based Approach. *TESOL Quarterly*, 39(3), 379-397.
- Duff, A. (2019). The effect of vocabulary intervention on text comprehension: who benefits? National Library of Medicine.
- Escandallo, J., & Baradillo, D. (2024). A sequential explanatory approach on the relationship between social literacy and student engagement as mediated by english speaking skills. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra1539>
- Gadd B. (2023). *Teaching pronunciation: A course book and reference book (2nd Edition)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Guo, D. (2020). Different strategies for effective pronunciation: a qualitative study. *KLHM Press*. Hode, A. S. (2022). Negotiating the local in English as a lingua franca. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 26, 197-218
- Jalla, K. (2019). A literature review on strategies for teaching pronunciation. Online Submission James, L. (2021). *Teaching the pronunciation of English as a lingua franca*. Oxford: Oxford University Jao, J (2021). *Phonemic Awareness Activities for Early Reading*

- Success. New York: Scholastic Juliana, Y. (2018). Metacognitive instruction in listening for young learners. *ELT Journal*, 60 (3), 222-232
- Khalif, A. (2019). Global pronunciation difficulty among ASEAN countries. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness. languages. Tesol Quarterly*, 25(3), 481-520.
- Lunberg, A. (2020). Applying peer tutoring to spelling at the elementary or spelling at the elementary level. Minnesota State University, Mankato.
- Mello, B. (2019) 'Pounding dice into musket balls: using wargames to teach the American revolution'. *The History Teacher* 46/4: 561–76.
- Nair, R., Krishnasamy, R., & De Mello, G. (2017). Rethinking the teaching of pronunciation in the ESL classroom. *The English Teacher*, 14 Press.
- Rost, M. (2002). *Teaching and Researching Listening*. Longman.
- Saidi, S. (2020). Effectiveness of dice games on young learners. *SCVH Journal for English as Foreign Language*.
- Saonah, S. (2018). Meningkatkan kemampuan membaca dan menulis permulaan dengan media gambar di kelas i sd negeri 222 pasir pogor. *Jurnal Elementaria Edukasia*, 1(1), 101–110.
- Thoms, B. (2021). The role of dice games on compound word stress in second language pronunciation development. *TESOL Quarterly*.
- Torgesen, J.K. (2018). "Intensive Remedial Instruction for Children with Severe Reading Difficulties: Immediate and Long-Term Outcomes from Two Instructional Approaches".
- Yihong, G., Yuan, Z., Ying, C., & Yan, Z. (2018). Relationship between English learning motivation types and self-identity changes among Chinese students. *Tesol Quarterly*, 41(1), 133-155.

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